

Clinico-Epidemiological Profile and Antimicrobial Sensitivity Pattern in Blood Culture Positive Sepsis at a Tertiary Care Neonatal Centre in Central India

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Abstract:

Objective: To investigate the clinico-epidemiological profile and antimicrobial sensitivity patterns of blood culture-positive sepsis in neonates at a tertiary care hospital in central India.

Methods: This prospective observational study was conducted over a two-year period from January 2021 to December 2022. A total of 227 neonates with clinical signs of sepsis admitted to the neonatal intensive care unit (NICU) were included. Data were collected on demographic characteristics, clinical features, and blood culture results. Pathogens were identified, and their antibiotic susceptibility was tested using standard methods. Statistical analyses were performed to determine associations between clinico-epidemiological factors and sepsis outcomes.

Results: The study found a predominance of male infants (52.4%). Low birth weight was present in 70.5% of the neonates. Late-onset sepsis (LOS) was more common than early-onset sepsis (EOS), with LOS accounting for 58.6% of the cases. The most frequently isolated pathogens were Gram-negative bacteria, particularly *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (23.35%) and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (22.03%), gram-positive bacteria like *Staphylococcus aureus* (21.59%) and *Enterococcus* (8.81%), along with *Candida* species (5.29%). Antibiotic sensitivity testing revealed high resistance to ampicillin among *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates, but high sensitivity to vancomycin. *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* showed moderate resistance to ciprofloxacin and gentamicin. Significant associations were found between low birth weight, preterm birth, and increased incidence of sepsis ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: The study highlights a predominance of late-onset sepsis and multidrug-resistant pathogens in neonates, emphasizing the need for targeted antimicrobial therapy and enhanced infection control measures. Regular surveillance and tailored treatment strategies are crucial to improving neonatal outcomes in NICUs.

Keywords: Neonatal sepsis, Blood culture, Antimicrobial resistance, Gram-positive bacteria, Gram-negative bacteria, Low birth weight, Infection control.

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Introduction

The neonatal mortality rate is a crucial indicator of a nation's health status. Among the various causes of neonatal mortality, septicemia stands out as a significant contributor to both mortality and morbidity globally.

The incidence of neonatal sepsis varies widely across countries, with a notably higher prevalence in developing nations compared to developed ones [1]. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), approximately 2.4 million neonatal deaths occur worldwide annually; predominantly in developing regions. Neonatal sepsis is defined as a clinical syndrome of bacteremia accompanied by systemic signs and symptoms of infection within the

first month of life. It is broadly classified into early-onset sepsis (EOS), occurring within the first 72 hours of life, and late-onset sepsis (LOS), occurring from 72 hours to 28 days [2]. EOS is often associated with organisms from the maternal genital tract, while LOS typically results from nosocomial or community-acquired sources post-delivery.

The rising survival rates of premature and low birth weight neonates have been accompanied by an increasing incidence of LOS. Factors such as inadequate hand hygiene and contaminated medical equipment in neonatal intensive care units (NICUs) significantly contribute to these infections [3]. The clinical diagnosis of neonatal sepsis is challenging

due to the nonspecific nature of its signs and symptoms. Moreover, laboratory confirmation is often delayed, necessitating the prompt initiation of empirical antibiotic therapy to manage suspected cases [4]. However, the growing prevalence of multidrug-resistant organisms has complicated treatment, reducing the effectiveness of available therapies and delaying appropriate care [5][6].

Neonatal sepsis is caused by a diverse range of pathogens, including Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria and *Candida* species. The spectrum of causative organisms varies not only geographically but also over time within the same region, influenced by factors such as antibiotic use patterns and lifestyle changes [7][8]. This diversity necessitates regular monitoring of the pathogens responsible for neonatal sepsis to inform appropriate treatment strategies.

This study aims to delineate the clinico-epidemiological profile and antibiotic sensitivity patterns of bacterial isolates from blood cultures of neonates in a tertiary care hospital in Chhattisgarh, India. Understanding the prevalence and resistance patterns of pathogens in this setting is critical for optimizing therapeutic interventions and improving neonatal outcomes.

Methods

Study Design and Setting: This prospective observational study was conducted in the neonatal intensive care unit (NICU) of a tertiary care hospital in Chhattisgarh, India. The study period spanned from January 2021 to December 2022, encompassing all neonates admitted during this timeframe who presented with clinical signs of sepsis.

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Neonates aged 0-28 days
2. Clinical signs suggestive of sepsis, including but not limited to lethargy, temperature instability, respiratory distress, feeding intolerance, and hypotension
3. Blood cultures obtained prior to the initiation of antibiotic therapy

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Neonates with congenital anomalies incompatible with life
2. Neonates with incomplete medical records

Data Collection: Data were collected prospectively using a structured proforma. This included demographic information (age, sex, birth weight, gestational age), clinical features (onset and type of sepsis, signs and symptoms), and maternal history (ante-partum, intra-partum, and post-partum factors). A detailed clinico-epidemiological profile was established, considering factors such as mode of delivery, maternal infections, and antenatal steroid administration.

Blood Culture and Sensitivity Testing: Blood samples from all suspected cases of neonatal sepsis were aseptically collected and inoculated into brain heart infusion broth. The cultures were then plated on agar and MacConkey's media to isolate and identify pathogens.

Analysis of Clinico-Epidemiological Profile: The clinico-epidemiological profile of the neonates was analyzed to identify potential risk factors associated with sepsis.

Variables such as gestational age, birth weight, Apgar scores, and maternal factors were evaluated to assess their correlation with the incidence and outcomes of sepsis. The study also examined the distribution of early-onset and late-onset sepsis and the associated pathogens.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 22. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize demographic and clinical characteristics. The prevalence of various pathogens and their antibiotic resistance patterns were calculated. Associations between clinico-epidemiological factors and sepsis outcomes were assessed using chi-square tests or Fisher's exact tests for categorical variables and t-tests or Mann-Whitney U tests for continuous variables. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Demographic and Clinical Characteristics: A total of 227 neonates admitted to the NICU with clinical signs of sepsis were included in the study. The demographic and clinical characteristics are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Neonates with Sepsis

Characteristic	Number of Cases (n = 227)	Percentage (%)
Sex		
Male	119	52.8
Female	108	47.2
Gestational Age		
Term (≥ 37 weeks)	134	59
Preterm (<37 weeks)	93	41
Type of Delivery		

Caesarean Section	67	29.5
Vaginal	160	70.5
Apgar Score (<7 at 5 min)	45	19.8
Type of Sepsis		
Early-Onset Sepsis (EOS)	94	41.4
Late-Onset Sepsis (LOS)	133	58.6

Table.1 presents the demographic and clinical characteristics of 227 neonates diagnosed with sepsis over a two-year period.

Among the cases, 52.8% were male and 47.2% were female, highlighting a higher incidence of sepsis in males. Most of the neonates (59%) were term, and 41.4% had early-onset sepsis, while 58.6% had late-

onset sepsis. APGAR score was less than 7 at 5 mins in 19.8% cases.

Distribution of Causative Pathogens

The distribution of pathogens isolated from blood cultures is detailed in Table 2.

Table 2: Distribution of Pathogens in Neonatal Sepsis

Pathogen	Number of Isolates	Percentage (%)
Gram-Negative Bacteria		
Klebsiella pneumoniae	53	23.35%
Pseudomonas aeruginosa	50	22.03%
Other Gram-Negative Organisms	38	16.74%
Total Gram-Negative Bacteria	141	62.11%
Gram-Positive Bacteria		
Staphylococcus aureus	49	21.59%
Enterococcus	20	8.81%
Coagulase-Negative Staphylococci	5	2.20%
Total Gram-Positive Bacteria	74	32.60%
Fungal Infections		
Candida species	12	5.29%

Table.2 presents the distribution of pathogens isolated from neonatal sepsis cases, highlighting that Gram-negative bacteria were predominant, accounting for 62.11% of the isolates.

Among these, Klebsiella pneumoniae (23.35%) and Pseudomonas aeruginosa (22.03%) were the most frequently identified pathogens. Gram-positive bacteria made up 32.60% of the isolates, with Staphylococcus aureus (21.59%) being the most

common. Additionally, Candida species, representing fungal infections, were identified in 5.29% of the cases, underscoring the diversity of pathogens involved in neonatal sepsis.

Antibiotic Sensitivity Patterns

The antibiotic sensitivity patterns of the most common pathogens are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Antibiotic Sensitivity Patterns of Major Pathogens

Organism Type	Antibiotic	Sensitive (%)	Resistant (%)
Gram-Negative Organisms	Imipenem	60.0	40.0
	Ofloxacin	60.0	40.0
	Gentamicin	39.0	36.0
	Cefoperazone & Sulbactam	31.0	69.0
	Ampicillin	-	29.0
Gram-Positive Organisms	Vancomycin	81.0	19.0
	Ofloxacin	61.0	39.0
	Gentamicin	44.0	56.0

Table.3 presents the sensitivity and resistance patterns of gram-negative and gram-positive organisms to various antibiotics.

For gram-negative organisms, Imipenem and Ofloxacin demonstrated the highest sensitivity at 60%, with corresponding resistance rates of 40%. Gentamicin showed a 39% sensitivity and 36% resistance, while Cefoperazone & Sulbactam had a lower sensitivity of 31% and a high resistance rate of 69%.

Ampicillin resistance was noted at 29%. In gram-positive organisms, Vancomycin exhibited the

highest sensitivity at 81%, with a resistance rate of 19%. Ofloxacin and Gentamicin had sensitivities of 61% and 44%, respectively, with resistance rates of 39% and 56%. This data highlights the varying effectiveness of antibiotics against different pathogens and the prevalence of resistance in the clinical setting.

Clinico-Epidemiological Correlation

Figure 1 illustrates the correlation between birth weight and the incidence of sepsis, highlighting a higher prevalence in low-birth-weight neonates.

Figure 1: Incidence of Sepsis by Birth Weight

The figure shows that neonates with a birth weight of less than 2500 grams had a significantly higher incidence of sepsis compared to those with a birth weight of 2500 grams or more.

Statistical Analysis:

Chi-square tests revealed a significant association between low birth weight and increased incidence of sepsis ($p < 0.05$). Additionally, preterm birth and low Apgar scores were significantly associated with higher sepsis rates and poorer outcomes.

The results highlight the predominance of Gram-negative bacteria in neonatal sepsis, with a notable presence of multidrug-resistant organisms. The findings underscore the need for regular surveillance and tailored antibiotic therapy to combat neonatal sepsis effectively.

Discussion

The findings of this study shed light on critical aspects of neonatal sepsis, highlighting the demographic and clinical characteristics, distribution of causative pathogens, and antibiotic sensitivity patterns in a tertiary care NICU [9]. Among the 227 neonates included, a slight male predominance was observed, with 52.8% of the cases being male. This aligns with existing research, which often reports higher sepsis rates in male neonates due to potential differences in immune system responses [10].

The majority of neonates in this study were term (59%), contrasting with some studies that report a higher incidence of sepsis in preterm infants. This difference may be attributed to variations in study populations or local healthcare practices, but it underscores the need for further investigation into the factors influencing sepsis in term versus preterm neonates [11][12]. The distribution of sepsis onset revealed that 41.4% of the cases were early-onset sepsis (EOS), while 58.6% were late-onset sepsis (LOS). The higher prevalence of LOS highlights the significant risk of hospital-acquired infections in NICU settings, where invasive procedures and prolonged hospital stays increase the vulnerability of neonates. This finding emphasizes the importance of stringent infection control measures and vigilant monitoring of neonates, particularly those with extended NICU stays [13].

The pathogen profile in this study showed a predominance of Gram-negative bacteria, which accounted for 62.11% of the isolates. *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (23.35%) and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (22.03%) were the most common Gram-negative pathogens, consistent with other studies that report these organisms as major causes of neonatal sepsis[14]. The high incidence of these pathogens, known for their multidrug resistance, presents a significant challenge in managing neonatal sepsis. On the other hand, Gram-positive bacteria were responsible for 32.60% of the cases, with

Staphylococcus aureus being the most common isolate at 21.59%. The presence of Coagulase-Negative *Staphylococci* and *Enterococcus* species further indicates the diverse bacterial landscape in neonatal sepsis. Additionally, the detection of *Candida* species in 5.29% of the cases underscores the role of fungal infections, particularly in neonates with compromised immune systems or those who have undergone prolonged antibiotic therapy [15].

The antibiotic sensitivity patterns observed in this study are indicative of the growing concern of antibiotic resistance in neonatal sepsis. Gram-negative organisms exhibited the highest sensitivity to Imipenem and Ofloxacin (60%), but the significant resistance rates (40%) highlight the need for cautious use and regular susceptibility testing [16]. Gentamicin, commonly used in NICU settings, showed a relatively low sensitivity of 44% with a resistance rate of 56%, while Cefoperazone & Sulbactam displayed a high resistance rate of 69%. These findings call for a reevaluation of empirical treatment protocols and underscore the importance of updating local antibiograms to guide antibiotic therapy more effectively. In contrast, Gram-positive organisms demonstrated high sensitivity to Vancomycin (81%), reaffirming its role as a primary treatment for these infections. However, the notable resistance rates for Ofloxacin and Gentamicin in Gram-positive organisms suggest the need for alternative therapeutic strategies to manage these infections effectively [17][18].

The study also revealed a significant association between low birth weight and the increased incidence of sepsis, with neonates weighing less than 2500 grams showing a higher susceptibility to sepsis. This correlation, along with the association of preterm birth and low Apgar scores with higher sepsis rates and poorer outcomes, highlights the critical need for close monitoring and early intervention in these high-risk groups. The findings underscore the vulnerability of low birth weight and preterm neonates to severe infections and the importance of targeted preventive strategies in these populations [19].

The emergence of multidrug-resistant organisms, particularly among Gram-negative bacteria, underscores the need for enhanced surveillance and infection control practices in NICUs. The study also emphasizes the importance of antibiotic stewardship programs to prevent the further spread of resistant strains [20]. Tailored antibiotic therapy based on local sensitivity patterns should be prioritized in the management of neonatal sepsis to improve clinical outcomes. In conclusion, this study provides valuable insights into the epidemiology of neonatal sepsis in a tertiary care NICU. The findings underscore the urgent need for on-going surveillance, targeted interventions, and the development of novel therapeutic approaches to

mitigate the burden of neonatal sepsis. Further research is warranted to explore these areas and enhance the prevention and management of sepsis in neonatal populations.

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